

New Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes of Substituted Aliphatic Thiosemicarbazides containing ONS Donor Sites

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Several new dioxouranium(VI) complexes of substituted aliphatic thiosemicarbazides derived from acetyl, propionyl, butyryl, isobutyryl, valeroyl and isovaleroyl hydrazines and phenyl isothiocyanate, have been synthesised of the general formula $[UO_2(HL)_2]$, where H_2L = tridentate monoanionic thiosemicarbazide. The substituted aliphatic thiosemicarbazides behave in a similar way to tridentate ligands via the amide nitrogen, thioketo and the enolic carbonyl oxygen, with replacement of a hydrogen atom from the latter group. Also, the bond between the thioketo group and uranyl ion is very weak. One of the more striking differences between these complexes and those prepared from substituted aromatic thiosemicarbazide is that the effects of CS in bonding and the absence of the solvent molecules.

In continuation of our earlier work¹ on ligands containing thiosemicarbazide moiety, we report herein the preparation and characterisation of new dioxouranium(VI) complexes derived from some aliphatic acid hydrazides and phenyl isothiocyanate ligands containing ONS donor sites. The anomalous behaviour of these ligands towards dioxouranium(VI) than those containing NO^2 , NN^3 , ONO^4 and ONN^5 moieties, promoted us to continue this study. Moreover, the nature of the weak bond formed between the thioketo group and the uranyl ion and its role on the properties of the complexes are discussed.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) are air-stable, partially soluble in MeOH and EtOH, easily soluble in DMF and DMSO but insoluble in other common organic non-polar solvents. The dioxouranium complexes have a general formula $[UO_2(HL)_2]$, where H_2L = tridentate monobasic thiosemicarbazide. The molar conductivities of all the complexes in DMSO (25°) are in the range 1.2–1.8 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, indicating their non-electrolytic nature⁶. The magnetic susceptibility data (at room temperature) indicate that the complexes are diamagnetic as expected for a f^0 -system. Molecular weight determinations suggest a monomeric structure for all the complexes.

The ir spectra (nujol) of the free ligands (1) exhibit three bands at 3 300–3 200 (N^4H), 3 210–3 140 (N^2H), 3 170–3 100 (N^1H), 1 710–1 670 (CO) and 975–940 cm^{-1} (N–N). The band position for the thioketo group was calculated by the method of Mecke *et al.*⁷, taking in consideration that the ratio of ν_{CO}/ν_{CS} is 1.5, and the values were found in the 1 133–1 113 cm^{-1} region and coincide more or less with the experimental values as shown in Table 2. The absence of any bands above 3 500 (OH) or

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		C	H	U
$[UO_2(APTS-H)_2]$ Brown	225	31.9 (31.5)	2.0 (2.9)	33.9 (34.7)
$[UO_2(PPTS-H)_2]$ Red	222	33.8 (33.6)	4.7 (3.4)	33.6 (33.3)
$[UO_2(BPTS-H)_2]$ Red	227	36.6 (35.6)	3.5 (3.8)	32.0 (32.0)
$[UO_2(IBPTS-H)_2]$ Brown	232	35.2 (35.6)	3.7 (3.8)	31.8 (32.0)
$[UO_2(VPTS-H)_2]$ Brown	212	38.4 (37.4)	4.9 (4.2)	31.5 (30.9)
$[UO_2(IVPTS-H)_2]$ Orange	233	37.5 (37.4)	4.8 (4.2)	31.1 (30.9)

*In DMSO.

2 600–2 500 cm^{-1} (SH), suggests that both CO and CS exist in the keto form. Also, the nmr spectra (DMSO) of the ligands show no signals due to OH or SH confirming the presence of the keto form (2). The two broad but weak bands at ca. 2 150 and 1 900 cm^{-1} are commensurate with intramolecular hydrogen bonding⁸ as shown in 2.

The ir spectra reveal that the ligands coordinate in a tridentate manner via the N^4H , CS and the enolised carbonyl oxygen with replacement of a hydrogen atom from the latter group. Before we discuss the mode of bonding we have to elucidate the tendency and the nature of the thioketo group

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TABLE 2—IMPORTANT IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) ASSIGNMENTS OF THE LIGAND COMPLEXES

Compd.	⁴ NH	² NH	¹ NH	CO	CS*	CS**	C—O	N—N	CS
APTS	3 270	3 210	3 140	1 690	1 127	—	—	990	740
[UO ₂ (APTS-H) ₂]	3 220	—	3 140	—	—	1 110	1 220	980	750
PPTS	3 260	3 220	3 140	1 690	1 127	—	—	960	740
[UO ₂ (PPTS-H) ₂]	3 220	—	3 140	—	—	1 120	1 225	970	750
BPTS	3 210	3 150	3 170	1 670	1 113	—	—	950	745
[UO ₂ (BPTS-H) ₂]	3 200	—	3 110	—	—	1 100	1 220	965	750
IBPTS	3 200	3 140	3 100	1 690	1 127	—	—	940	750
[UO ₂ (IBPTS-H) ₂]	3 190	—	3 100	—	—	1 125	1 220	955	745
VPTS	3 250	3 190	3 160	1 695	1 130	—	—	940	750
[UO ₂ (VPTS-H) ₂]	3 230	—	3 120	—	—	1 123	1 230	940	745
IVPT	3 300	3 180	3 160	1 700	1 133	—	—	940	745
[UO ₂ (IVPTS-H) ₂]	3 260	—	3 160	—	—	3 115	1 195	955	740

*Cald. **expt.

towards uranyl ion. It is well known⁹ that the sulphur atom has a little tendency towards uranyl ion in comparison to oxygen or nitrogen according to the definition of Pearson¹⁰. But in our case, we found that the properties of the isolated complexes are completely different than those containing NO, NOO and/or NNO as donor sites. For example, the melting points of the thiosemicarbazide complexes are low and they are deeply coloured. This leads to suggest the contribution of the sulphur atom by one way or other in bonding. The small negative shifts (10–33 cm^{-1}) of the thioketo group to lower wavenumber indicate the involvement of CS in bonding. Two structures through which the thioketo group can be involved in bonding are proposed. Firstly, the thioketo and the NH groups associated with the uranyl ion lie in the same plane while the carbonyl oxygen exists in another plane (3). Secondly, the carbonyl oxygen and NH groups together with the uranyl ion exist in the same plane while the thioketo group in another plane (4). Structure 3 is more favourable than 4 since the bond

formed in the first case is mainly through σ -bonding while in the latter case through π -bonding, due to the overlap of $d(\text{sulphur}) - d(\text{UO}_2^{2+})$ or $d(\text{sulphur}) - f(\text{UO}_2^{2+})$. Consequently, the presence of σ -bonding causes the lowering of melting points of the complexes. The partial solubility of the complexes in MeOH and EtOH leads to assume that the bond between the thioketo group and uranyl ion is either ruptured and replaced by a solvent molecules (5), since the oxygen of the solvent has a great affinity towards uranyl ion than the sulphur atom, or the solvent makes a bridge between the uranyl ion and the thioketo group via hydrogen bonding (6) as discussed earlier¹.

We believe that structure 6 is more convenient than 5 since the complexes are deeply coloured. This colour is attributed to transfer of charge from sulphur to uranyl ion ($L \rightarrow M$) which proceeds via hydrogen bonding through the solvent molecule. In contrast, the charge transfer can not proceed through structure 5. The involvement of the other

TABLE 3—UV AND IR SPECTRAL DATA, FORCE CONSTANT AND BOND LENGTH OF O=U=O VIBRATION FOR THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	O=U=O frequency bands			F _{UO} mdyne/Å	RUO (Å)	¹ E _g → ³ π _u
	γ ₃	γ ₁	γ ₄			
[UO ₂ (APTS-H) ₂]	880	800	260	6.392	1.752	18 900
[UO ₂ (PPTS-H) ₂]	918	808	250	6.956	1.736	20 100
[UO ₂ (BPTS-H) ₂]	917	810	250	6.941	1.736	20 000
[UO ₂ (IBPTS-H) ₂]	918	805	260	6.956	1.736	18 900
[UO ₂ (VPTS-H) ₂]	875	805	255	6.319	1.754	18 900
[UO ₂ (IVPTS-H) ₂]	920	820	260	6.986	1.735	21 000

two coordination sites, i.e. NH and the enolised carbonyl oxygen is suggested on the basis of the following evidence.

The ν_{NH} and ν_{CO} bands disappear together with the appearance of new bands at 1 620–1 615 (C=N)¹¹ and 1 230–1 195 cm⁻¹ (C–O). The new bands appearing at 560–540 and 430–360 cm⁻¹ are attributed ν_{UO}¹¹ and ν_{UN}¹² vibrations, respectively. The obscure NH signal in the nmr spectra is taken as additional evidence for the enolisation of the carbonyl oxygen.

The uranyl complexes exhibit three bands at ca. 920, 810 and 260 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν₃, ν₁ and ν₄ vibration, respectively. The observation of only one vibration for each of ν₃, ν₁ and ν₄ modes suggests a monomeric structure¹³. The force constant (F) for the O=U=O vibration was calculated by the method of McGlynn *et al.*¹⁴ and the values are given in Table 3. Also, the U–O bond distance was calculated as mentioned earlier¹⁵. The electronic spectra of the uranyl complexes exhibit a band at 23 000–21 400 cm⁻¹ assigned to the ¹E_g→³π_u transition. Also, the presence of a band at 18 500–17 100 cm⁻¹ suggests that the uranyl ion is surrounded by four equatorial groups^{16,17}. This band may be assigned to n→π* transition for the thioketo group.

Differential scanning calorimetry measurements show only one exothermic peak for all uranyl complexes which coincide with the temperature of decomposition (Table 1). Also, this indicates the obscure nature of the solvent molecules which has been observed in the analogous complexes derived from aromatic thiosemicarbazides¹.

In conclusion, the involvement of the thioketo group in bonding with the uranyl ion proceeds in a very weak manner and it can be substituted easily by a solvent molecule (MeOH or EtOH) on dissolution. This bond has a great influence on the physical properties of the uranyl complexes especially colour and melting point. This phenomenon is verified on comparing the properties of the isolated complexes with those separated from ligands containing NN, NO, NNO and/or NOO donor sites. And in spite of the ligands containing both O, N and S as donor

atoms, the effect of the sulphur atom is much greater than the other two. Finally, the position of the ν_{CS} band was determined carefully using the ratio ν_{CS}/ν_{CO} equals to 1.5.

Experimental

Ligands (1) were synthesised as reported earlier¹: RC(O)N¹HN²HC(S)N⁴HPh (1), R=Me (APTS, m.p. 160°), Et (PPTS, m.p. 158°), n-Pr (BPTS, m.p. 110°), Me₂CH (IBPTS, m.p. 158°), n-Bu (VPTS, m.p. 150°) and Me₂CHCH₂ (IVPTS, m.p. 136°).

The preparative techniques as well as instruments used in the present study were identical to our previous work¹.

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